

Data Management Plan for "Development of an Eye Movement Analysis-Based Screening Tool for Reading Proficiency Assessment "

Version 1

Description

The Data Management Plan is developed for the project "Development of an Eye Movement Analysis-Based Screening Tool for Reading Proficiency Assessment" (research application No.1.1.1.9/LZP/2/25/199 under Activity 1.1.1.9. "Post-doctoral Research").The project focuses on evaluating the feasibility of wearable eye-tracking glasses for assessing eye movements during reading and reading-related tasks, as well as on the development of an automated tool for the analysis of reading-related eye movements, aimed at identifying children with reading difficulties based on recorded eye movement data.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grant

1.1.1.9 Research application No.1.1.1.9/LZP/2/25/199 of the Activity "Post-doctoral Research"

Researchers

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Organizations

University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Data Management Plan for "Development of an Eye Movement Analysis-Based Screening Tool for Reading Proficiency Assessment "](#)

Description:

The Data Management Plan is developed for the project "Development of an Eye Movement Analysis-Based Screening Tool for Reading Proficiency Assessment" (research application No.1.1.1.9/LZP/2/25/199 under Activity 1.1.1.9. "Post-doctoral Research"). The project focuses on evaluating the feasibility of wearable eye-tracking glasses for assessing eye movements during reading and reading-related tasks, as well as on the development of an automated tool for the analysis of reading-related eye movements, aimed at identifying children with reading difficulties based on recorded eye movement data.

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Organizations:

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Latvian Council of Science](#) | [LCS](#)

Grants: [1.1.1.9 Research application No.1.1.1.9/LZP/2/25/199 of the Activity "Post-doctoral Research"](#)

Project:

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

Publication Date: 2026-04-09

4. Templates

Descriptions

Dataset

This section describes the raw eye-tracking data collected during text reading in Latvian, recorded using Tobii Pro Fusion and Pupil Labs Neon eye-tracking devices. The data were collected within the framework of the project "Development of an Eye Movement Analysis-Based Screening Tool for Reading Proficiency Assessment" (research application No. 1.1.1.9/LZP/2/25/199, Activity 1.1.1.9. "Post-doctoral Research").

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The data are collected during text reading in Latvian, recorded using Tobii Pro Fusion and Pupil Labs Neon eye-tracking devices, to support the development of an automated tool for the analysis of reading-related eye movements.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

CSV

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

10

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

I have not considered re-using any of the existing data, because the dataset needed for this project is unique and is collected specifically for our experimental design.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

These data may be useful to researchers studying eye movements during reading.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

DataverseLV

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

The dataset is provided as a CSV file, which can be accessed using standard software such as Microsoft Excel.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2028-10-31

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Evita Šerpa (0000-0002-0427-9083)

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Encryption
- Firewall
- Passwords

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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